

THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN FOREIGN LANGUAGE SPEAKING ANXIETY AND ORAL PROFICIENCY AMONG BSED ENGLISH STUDENTS OF KOLEHIYO NG PANTUKAN

Monica P. Lomocso, Wendelyn M. Ojayas, Darie Jay M. Samiana,
Felix Jr. D. Tubera

College of Teacher Education, Kolehiyo ng Pantukan, Pantukan, Davao de Oro Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15739433>

ABSTRACT

This quantitative study investigated the relationship between foreign language speaking anxiety (FLSA) and oral proficiency among 350 Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) English majors in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan. The study aimed to examine the relationship between foreign language speaking anxiety (FLSA) and oral proficiency, with the hypothesis that a significant correlation exists between the two variables. Data were gathered through a combination of adapted and researcher-designed questionnaires aimed at assessing foreign language speaking anxiety (FLSA) and oral proficiency. The evaluation covered key components including fluency, comprehension, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar. The results indicated a weak yet statistically significant positive correlation. However, the low coefficient of determination suggests that foreign language speaking anxiety (FLSA) has only a minimal impact on the various aspects of oral communication. Other factors, including teacher feedback and supportive learning environments, played a more significant role. The study's findings highlighted the complexity of the FLSA-oral proficiency relationship and underscored the importance of creating positive learning environment that mitigated anxiety and promoted student engagement. The contribution lies in providing empirical evidence of the multifaceted nature of FLSA's influence on oral proficiency, suggesting a need for pedagogical approaches that address both anxiety management and the development of comprehensive oral communication skills.

Keywords: *Language education, foreign language speaking anxiety, oral proficiency, descriptive-quantitative, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Oral Proficiency is the ability to speak a language fluently and accurately in real-life situations. Mastering oral proficiency is all about effectively and fluently communicating in spoken language and actively engaging with others throughout the learning process. This skill encompasses participating in discussions, asking insightful questions, and meaningfully responding to peers and instructors. It emphasizes that strong oral communication skills significantly boost students' learning engagement, underscoring the critical role of interactive oral activities in improving educational outcomes (Apat et al., 2021).

In Saudi Arabia, English as a Foreign Language learners face significant challenges in developing oral proficiency due to factors like shyness, peer pressure, anxiety, and limited exposure to English in their daily lives (Alrasheedi, 2020). These obstacles hinder active engagement and interaction in the learning environment, which are crucial for enhancing speaking skills. In the Philippines, a study conducted by Chentez et al. (2019), identified prevalent issues in oral proficiency among high school students, particularly oral communication, and infrequent English usage. These challenges are primarily attributed to limited practice opportunities and nervousness when speaking English. In addition, the research demonstrates that incorporating interactive teaching methods and active learning strategies, such as role-playing, games, group discussions, and collaborative learning, can significantly enhance oral proficiency. These methods provide students with more practice opportunities, reduce anxiety, and encourage active engagement and interaction in learning. Consequently, these strategies foster improved communication skills and increased confidence in students.

Locally, in Tagum City, Davao del Norte, it has been observed that most students lack oral proficiency in English. This issue is often attributed to the limited time allocated for oral practice in classrooms and the scarcity of conversational opportunities outside of the educational setting, particularly in contexts where English is taught as a foreign language. Nonetheless, these deficiencies may arise from prevalent myths held by students about foreign language communication, such as the belief that one must have perfect pronunciation, a strong accent, a vast vocabulary, and comprehensive grammar knowledge. Additionally, despite excelling in English classes, many learners still struggle with real-life interactions (Pascual, 2019).

The research highlights a notable gap in comprehending the relationship between Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety and Oral Proficiency among English learners. It points out that past studies, such as "Speaking Anxiety and Language Proficiency among EFL at a University in Vietnam," have been insufficient and lacked empirical support, particularly regarding active participation and interaction in the learning process (Dung, 2020). This study aims to address these gaps by raising awareness among English majors about the multifaceted nature of anxiety and its impact on oral proficiency. It seeks to develop effective teaching methods to enhance the psychological well-being and academic achievement of BSED English students. Ultimately, the goal is to create a supportive educational atmosphere that fosters resilience and confidence in future educators.

Research Questions

The study aimed to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of foreign language speaking anxiety among BSED English students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan in terms of:
 - 1.1 communication apprehension;
 - 1.2 speaking anxiety; and
 - 1.3 fear of negative evaluation?
2. What is the level of oral proficiency among BSED English students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan in terms of:
 - 2.1 fluency;
 - 2.2 pronunciation;
 - 2.3 grammar;
 - 2.4 comprehension; and
 - 2.5 vocabulary?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized quantitative research method. Quantitative research is an approach that values breadth, statistical descriptions, and venerability (Barroga & Mantanguihan, 2020). It enables the creation of forecasts, the discovery of trends and averages, the investigation of causal linkages, and the extrapolation of results to larger populations. To collect quantitative data, researchers commonly use operational definitions to convert abstract ideas into observable and quantifiable measurements (Bhandari, 2021). It also employed descriptive-correlational design that assessed the statistical relationship between the two variables with no influence from any extraneous variable. It is useful to establish a link or influence of one variable from another variable (Creswell, 2014). The subject and respondents of this study were all BSED English major students currently enrolled in the academic year 2024-2025.

The researchers used adapted survey questionnaires for the level of foreign language speaking anxiety and researcher-made survey questionnaires for the level of oral proficiency. The questionnaire was the tool in gathering the data on the interplay between foreign language anxiety and oral proficiency among BSED English students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan. Part 1 deals with the independent variable which consists of 15 questions, 5 questions per indicator, while the dependent variable consists of 25 questions, 5 questions per indicator, a total of 40 items. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale with wherein 5 (always), 4 (often), 3 (sometimes) 2 (seldom) and 1 (never). To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, it undergone content validity and was checked, finalized, and validated by three experts before being used in the study.

For the level of foreign language speaking anxiety, the researchers employed the following parameter limits. For the level of oral proficiency, the researchers employed the following parameter limits.

To analyze the data gathered in the study, the researchers utilized three statistical tools. The mean was used to assess the level of foreign language speaking anxiety and oral proficiency among BSED-English students of Kolehiyo ng Pantukan, addressing the first two research questions. The Pearson-r correlation coefficient determined the relationship between anxiety and oral proficiency, answering the third question. Lastly, probability (p-value) was applied to decide on the acceptance or rejection of the null hypothesis, with lower p-values indicating stronger evidence against the null.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presented in Table 1 is the mean score of foreign language speaking anxiety of students in terms of communication apprehension. Data show the obtained, overall mean score of 3.68 this means that the level of foreign language speaking anxiety in terms of communication apprehension is high.

Table 1
Level of Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety of Students
in Terms of Communication Apprehension

Items	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. I like participating in group discussions.	3.81	High
2. I like to get involved in group discussions.	3.76	High
3. I am nervous when I must participate in a meeting.	3.71	High
4. I am very calm and relaxed when asked to express an opinion at a meeting.	3.52	High
5. I am very tense and nervous in conversations	3.58	High
Overall Mean	3.68	High

Table 1 data indicates the mean level of different items under communication apprehension that is based on the means score from the highest to the lowest, *I like participating in group discussion*, which got the highest mean score of 3.81. with the descriptive level indicated as high; followed by 3.76 for, *I like to get involved in group discussions*; 3.52, *I am very calm and relaxed when asked to express an opinion at a meeting*, with the description of high which means that the Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety in terms of Communication apprehension is oftentimes manifested among the respondents of the study.

Table 2
Level of Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety of Students
in Terms of Speaking Anxiety

Items	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. I am tense and nervous while participating in group discussions.	3.68	High
2. Engaging in a group discussion with new people makes me tense and nervous.	3.59	High
3. I have a rapid palpitation while participating in group discussion.	3.39	Moderate
4. Communicating at meetings usually makes me uncomfortable.	3.35	Moderate
5. I have a feeling of helplessness in speaking during conversation.	3.33	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.48	Moderate

Presented in Table 2 is the mean score of foreign language speaking anxiety of students in terms of speaking anxiety. Data show the obtained, overall mean score of 3.48 this means that the level of foreign language speaking anxiety in terms of speaking anxiety is moderate.

Data show the mean level of different items under speaking anxiety is based on means from the highest to the lowest. *I am tense and nervous while participating in group discussions* got the highest mean of 3.68, with the description of high; followed by 3.59 for, *engaging in a group discussion with new people makes me tense and nervous*. The item that got the lowest mean score of 3.35 is *Communicating at meetings usually makes me uncomfortable*, with the descriptive level of moderate. This means that the overall result indicated in the overall mean of 3.48 states that the level of foreign language speaking anxiety in terms of speaking anxiety is sometimes manifested.

Based on the results in Table 2 emphasized that speaking skills in terms of *I am tense and nervous while participating in group discussions* has an impact on the oral proficiency of English students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan. Speaking Anxiety in group discussions reveals that this condition is significantly influenced by fear of negative evaluation and the presence of unfamiliar individuals. In the study conducted by Young (2022), it emphasized

that heightened tension and nervousness are common in group settings, where individuals worry about being judged negatively by others, which is shaped by personal fear and social dynamics, ultimately affecting an individual's willingness and comfort in participating in group discussions. Furthermore, Montijo (2022) commented that group work sometimes can rise to an increase in anxiety driven by peer pressure and fear of bad evaluation and can be decreased where structured group activities with clear functions would lead to supportive peer interactions for good and engaging learning.

Table 3
Level of Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety of Students in Terms of Fear of Negative Evaluation of Students

Items	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. I have a feeling of being judged when speaking.	3.70	High
2. I over think that during conversation, my peers will be little me.	3.57	High
3. I am afraid to express myself at meetings.	3.51	High
4. I have the feeling of that everyone will judge me as I talk.	3.65	High
5. I feel very nervous while participating in a new conversation with new acquaintance.	3.67	High
Overall Mean	3.62	High

Presented in Table 3 are the mean scores of foreign languages speaking anxiety in terms of Fear of negative evaluation. Data show that the overall obtained mean 3.62 with the descriptive level described as high. This means that the level of foreign language speaking anxiety in terms of fear of negative evaluation is oftentimes manifested.

Data shows the mean level of different items under Fear of negative evaluation is based on means scores from the highest to lowest. *I have a feeling of being judged when speaking*, got the highest mean of 3.70, followed by 3.67, *I feel very nervous while participating in a new conversation with a new acquaintance*. The item that got the lowest mean score of 3.51 is *I am afraid to express myself at meetings*, all the items got high level that means the level of foreign language speaking anxiety in terms of fear of negative evaluation of students is oftentimes observed.

The results were supported by Cooper and Brownell (2020), which they emphasized that the most prevailing reason contributing to anxiety among students in an active learning environment is fear of negative evaluation. This will deter a student in taking part in class discussions and activities. This claim was supported by Aliyu et al. (2019), emphasized

that the fear of negative evaluation significantly influences student's oral communication skills and overall participation in learning activities. They explained that both structured oral presentations and interactive in-class sessions may reduce this type of fear since students would have more practice and get constructive feedback.

Table 4
Summary on the Level of Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety of Students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
A. Communication Apprehension	3.68	High
B. Speaking Anxiety	3.48	Moderate
C. Fear of Negative Evaluation	3.62	High
Overall Mean	3.59	High

Reflected in Table 4 is the summary on the level of foreign language speaking anxiety of students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan. The data revealed that the overall mean score of 3.59 described as high which signifies that the level of foreign language speaking anxiety is oftentimes manifested among students.

The result emphasized that foreign language speaking anxiety has significant role that impacts on communication apprehension. Moreover, judgment and social anxiety issues typically prevent involvement in group activities, and communication and teamwork become restricted (Brown, 2020). However, Demir, Cinar & Keskin (2023) revealed that there are individuals who actively take part in group discussions and can gain some significant advantages like improved learning outcomes and communication skills. The paradox is the complexity of the impact that the engagement of an individual in group activity has, which may be either positive or negative, depending on a person's own experiences and tolerance levels.

In addition, Zhang (2021), explained that anxiety meeting is also a form of communication apprehension that is generally caused by fear of judgment or low self-confidence. Those who are comfortable and confident, particularly those familiar with the subject matter at hand, have a better chance to express their messages more constructively. This is to highlight the significance of individual difference awareness in communication processes and the necessity for learning processes that build confidence and minimize tension, ultimately leading to a more caring and effective learning environment.

Table 5
Level of Oral Proficiency of Students in Terms of Fluency

Items	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. I pronounce words clearly and correctly.	3.33	Moderate
2. I speak at a natural pace, without noticeable hesitations.	3.23	Moderate
3. I can speak without being distracted by my surroundings	3.19	Moderate
4. I maintain a consistent and appropriate flow of speech, even when discussing challenging topics.	3.18	Moderate
5. I feel confident and comfortable expressing myself orally in various situations.	3.08	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.20	Moderate

Presented in Table 5 are the mean scores of oral proficiencies in terms fluency. Data show that the overall obtained mean 3.20 with the descriptive level described as moderate. This means that the fluency among English major students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan is sometimes observed.

Data indicate that the mean level of different items on fluency is based on means scores from the highest to the lowest are the following: 3.33 for, *I pronounce words clearly and correctly* with the descriptive level described as moderate. Followed by 3.23 for, *I speak at a natural pace, without noticeable hesitations* with the descriptive level described as moderate. Lastly, 3.08 for, *I feel confident and comfortable expressing myself orally in various situations*. In the study of De Jong (2023), it highlighted the negative correlation between in induced speaking and fluency, noting that higher anxiety levels resulted in increased pauses, adversely affecting overall fluency. This exploration of speaking anxiety and its impact on oral proficiency has garnered significant attention in recent research (Aliyu et al. 2019).

Presented in Table 6 are the means score of oral proficiencies in terms of pronunciation. Data show that the overall obtained mean 3.18, means that the pronunciation towards oral proficiency is moderate. Data indicate that the mean level of different items on pronunciation is based on means from the highest to the lowest are the following: 3.30 for, *I pronounce words clearly during conversations*, with a description of sometimes. Followed by 3.24 for, *I use to correct intonation and stress patterns while speaking*. Lastly, 3.09 is the lowest mean for, *I find it easy to pronounce unfamiliar words correctly*. All the items got the description of sometimes which means that the level of oral proficiency in terms of pronunciation is sometimes manifested.

Table 6
Level of Oral Proficiency of Students in Terms of Pronunciation

Items	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. I pronounce words clearly during conversations.	3.30	Moderate
2. I find it easy to pronounce unfamiliar words correctly.	3.09	Moderate
3. I understand without having to ask for clarification.	3.12	Moderate
4. When speaking in a foreign language, I often feel confident about my pronunciation	3.14	Moderate
5. I use to correct intonation and stress patterns while speaking.	3.24	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.18	Moderate

In the research conducted by Male (2018) revealed that students consistently demonstrated a negative relationship between foreign language anxiety and learner's self-assessed pronunciation abilities. Anxious learners reported lower levels of pronunciation competence, while those with those with reduced anxiety expressed greater confidence in their skills. Furthermore the correlation between foreign language speaking anxiety and self-assisted speaking proficiency. Their study revealed that higher speaking anxiety was linked to lower self-assessed proficiency in pronunciation.

To justify these claims, Rood, and De Jong (2023) expanded the discussion by examining the effects of induced speaking anxiety on cognitive fluency in language learners. Their mixed-methods study found that increased anxiety was associated with a higher frequency of silent and filled pauses, negatively impacting pronunciation.

Presented in Table 7 are the means score of oral proficiencies in terms grammar. Data show that the overall obtained mean 3.25 with the descriptive level described as moderate, this means that the level of oral proficiency in terms of grammar is sometimes manifested.

Data indicate that the mean level of different items on grammar is based on means score from the highest to the lowest are the following: 3.45 for, *I make grammatical errors in my writing*. Followed by *sometimes*. 3.27 for, *my formal writing demonstrates strong grammatical knowledge*. Lastly, 3.13 is the lowest mean for, *I receive positive feedback on my grammar usage from peers and teacher*, described as *sometimes* which indicates that the oral proficiency of students in terms of grammar is moderate.

Table 7
Level of Oral Proficiency of Students in terms of Grammar

Items	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. I make grammatical errors in my writing.	3.45	Moderate
2. I feel confident in my understanding and use of English grammar.	3.23	Moderate
3. I use correct grammar when speaking in English	3.17	Moderate
4. My formal writing demonstrates strong grammatical knowledge.	3.27	Moderate
5. I receive positive feedback on my grammar usage from peers and teacher.	3.13	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.25	Moderate

The research revealed that anxious learners were less inclined to utilize complex grammatical structures, which ultimately impacted their overall oral proficiency (Male, 2018). Further reinforcing this perspective explored the impact of speaking anxiety on English language learners. The findings indicated that speaking anxiety significantly affected learners, leading to a limited use of grammatical structure.

Presented in Table 8 are the mean scores of oral proficiencies in terms comprehension. Data show that the overall obtained mean 3.28 with the descriptive level of moderate. This means that the comprehension towards oral proficiency is moderate and sometimes observed.

Table 8 indicates that the mean level of different items on comprehension is based on means scores from the highest to the lowest are the following: 3.37 for, *I can easily understand the main ideas in English text*, with a description of *sometimes*. Followed by 3.31 for, *I comprehend spoken English during conversations and lectures*. with the description of *sometimes*. Lastly, 3.20 are the lowest mean for, *I can understand complex or technical English texts without much difficulty* and the *I follow spoken instructions in English accurately*, described as *sometimes* which indicates that the oral proficiency of students in terms of comprehension is moderate.

Based on the results above, it shows that comprehension has a higher impact on oral proficiency. Saeed (2024) conducted a study about the significant contribution of anxiety to learners Comprehension. The findings revealed that anxious learners struggled to listen and understand spoken language, which adversely affected their oral proficiency.

Table 8
Level of Oral Proficiency of Students in Terms of Comprehension

Items	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. I can easily understand the main ideas in English text.	3.37	Moderate
2. I comprehend spoken English during conversations and lectures.	3.31	Moderate
3. I can understand complex or technical English texts without much difficulty.	3.20	Moderate
4. I follow spoken instructions in English accurately.	3.30	Moderate
5. I can infer the meaning of unfamiliar words in context while reading English texts.	3.20	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.28	Moderate

In addition, Jiang and Dewale (2020) examined the relationship between speaking anxiety and self-perceived proficiency in comprehension among foreign language speaking anxiety. Their research found a correlation between increased speaking anxiety and decreased self-perceived proficiency in understanding spoken language. This suggests that anxiety is not only affects learner's performance but also their confidence in their comprehension abilities. Reflected in Table 9 is the summary of the oral proficiency of students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan. The data revealed that the overall mean of 3.22 got a description of sometimes. The overall mean signifies that the level of the foreign language speaking anxiety among BSED students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan is moderate. To examine further, the indicator with the highest mean of 3.28 is comprehension, the grammar 3.25; pronunciation and vocabulary has the lowest mean of 3.18 all the indicators got description of sometimes.

The results emphasized that oral proficiency has a significant role that impacts comprehension. Saeed (2024) conducted research that established learners who were anxious had serious problems with listening and comprehending what is being communicated orally, thereby affecting their oral ability negatively. This evidence illustrates the need for establishing friendly learning environments that may minimize anxiety as well as enhance comprehension ability in language learners.

Table 9
Level of Oral Proficiency of Students in Terms of Vocabulary

Items	Mean	Descriptive Level
1. I have a broad range of English vocabulary.	3.09	Moderate
2. I use appropriate vocabulary in various contexts.	3.17	Moderate
3. I find it easy to learn and remember new English words.	3.17	Moderate
4. I can use diverse vocabulary when speaking in English.	3.21	Moderate
5. I know a wide range of synonyms for common English words.	3.26	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.18	Moderate

Subsequent research by Pascual (2019) established a correlation between speaking anxiety and self-rated comprehension proficiency among foreign language learners. The study confirmed that there were high levels of speaking anxiety among learners with low levels of confidence when understanding oral language. This indicates that not only does anxiety impede learners' performance but also reduces their confidence in comprehension abilities, which requires intervention to address anxiety to improve learners' oral language processing skills. Supporting these observations, Winaryo (2021) also investigated the influence of foreign language anxiety on performance and comprehension of oral communication. The study revealed that anxiety has a negative influence on the understanding of the oral language among students, which contributes to miscommunication and lesser participation in oral practice.

These observations show that removing anxiety could positively enhance the learners' proficiency and comprehension in oral communication, complementing the recommendation for the elimination of anxiety from language learning environments. The results emphasized that oral proficiency has a significant role that impacts comprehension and elucidated that learners who were anxious had serious problems with listening and comprehending what is being communicated orally, thereby affecting their oral ability negatively. This evidence illustrates the need for establishing friendly learning environments that may minimize anxiety as well as enhance comprehension ability in language learners, (Saeed, 2024).

Subsequent research by Han, Li & Haider (2022) established a correlation between speaking anxiety and self-rated comprehension proficiency among foreign language learners. The study confirmed that there were high levels of speaking anxiety among learners with low levels of confidence when understanding oral language. This indicates that not only does anxiety impede learners' performance but also reduces their confidence in comprehension abilities, which requires intervention to address anxiety to improve learners' oral language processing skills.

Table 10
Summary on the Level of Oral Proficiency among Students
in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Fluency	3.20	Moderate
Pronunciation	3.18	Moderate
Grammar	3.25	Moderate
Comprehension	3.28	Moderate
Vocabulary	3.18	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.22	Moderate

In the study conducted by Fiveable, Okoro, Priest & Patton (2022), investigated the influence of foreign language anxiety on performance and comprehension of oral communication. The study revealed that anxiety has a negative influence on the understanding of the oral language among students, which contributes to miscommunication and lesser participation in oral practice. These observations show that removing anxiety could positively enhance the learners' proficiency and comprehension in oral communication, complementing the recommendation for the elimination of anxiety from language learning environments.

Displayed in Table 11 is the significant relationship between the level of foreign language speaking anxiety and oral proficiency of students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan. The data revealed the r-value is 0.11 which indicates a weak positive correlation. This means that the foreign language speaking anxiety directly proportional with oral proficiency of the students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan.

On the other hand, the result of p-value is 0.04 which is less than 0.05 level of significance which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the level of foreign language speaking anxiety and oral proficiency among BSED students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan.

The Coefficient of the determination (r^2) of 01 means that 01% of the variation in the oral proficiency of students is attributed of their foreign language speaking anxiety. The remaining 99% is the chance of variation and is attributed to the other factors that are not covered in the present study such as motivation and attitude, teaching methods and socioeconomic status, peer influence and interaction psychological factors (Dornyei and Csizer, 2002). It is therefore figured out that the Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety has a significant relationship to the Oral Proficiency of Students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan.

Table 11

Significance on the Relationship Between the Level Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety and Oral Proficiency of Students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan

VARIABLES	r-Value	Interpretation	p-value a=0.05	Decision on Ho	Conclusion on Relationship
Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety	0.11	Weak Positive Correlation	0.04	Rejected	Significant
Oral Proficiency					
		Coefficient of Determination	0.01		

Conclusions

The findings of the study were as follows:

1. The foreign language speaking anxiety of students in terms of communication apprehension with the corresponding mean of 3.68; in terms of speaking anxiety with the corresponding mean of 3.48; in terms of fear of negative evaluation with the corresponding mean of 3.62. The overall mean is 3.59 described as high.
2. The level of oral proficiency of students in terms of fluency with a corresponding mean of 3.20; in terms of pronunciation with a corresponding mean of 3.18; in terms of grammar with the corresponding mean of 3.25; in terms of comprehension with the corresponding mean of 3.28; in terms of vocabulary with the corresponding mean of 3.18. The overall mean is 3.22 described as moderate.
3. There is a significant relationship between foreign language speaking anxiety and oral proficiency of students in Kolehiyo ng Pantukan.

Recommendations

1. Students may focus on building their confidence by engaging in regular, low-pressure speaking practice and seeking supportive environments to help reduce language-speaking anxiety.
2. Teachers may continue to create a more supportive classroom environment that encourages stress-free, frequent oral practice, and provides constructive feedback to help students manage anxiety and improve language proficiency.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby declare that the study was conducted with strict adherence to ethical standards. Informed consent was duly obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the research. Respondents were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any stage without facing any consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained, and all identifying information was protected. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the process. The authors affirm that there was no conflict of interest that could have influenced the conduct or results of the study. Furthermore, plagiarism was rigorously avoided, and academic honesty was always observed. The analysis and interpretation of the data were carried out objectively, without any form of bias. Finally, the results of this study were used solely for academic and research purposes.

Acknowledgments

The successful completion of this thesis was made possible through the unwavering guidance, support, and contributions of several individuals and institutions. The researchers express deep gratitude to the Almighty Father for His boundless grace and love. Special thanks go to Dr. Eufrosina P. Mines, Vice-President for Academics and Research, for her expertise and leadership as defense panel chair, and to Mr. Felix Jr. D. Tubera, their adviser, for his constant support and invaluable guidance. The researchers also acknowledge Dr. Nitchell A. Acedillo, Acting College President, for permitting the study on campus, and the Kolehiyo ng Pantukan Library for granting access to vital resources. Appreciation is extended to the thesis committee—Dr. Celedonia Coquilla, Dr. Quennie A. Cunanan, and Dr. Mharfe M. Micaroz—for their insightful feedback and encouragement. Lastly, heartfelt thanks are given to the English Major students from first to fourth year who served as respondents, whose participation greatly enriched this research.

REFERENCES

- Aliyu, M. M., Korau, S. M., & Basiru, A. (2019). Reducing Undergraduates Speaking Anxiety through Class Interactions and Oral Presentations. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1265915>
- Alrasheedi, S. (2020). Investigation of Factors Influencing Speaking Performance of Saudi EFLearners. *Arab World English Journal*, 11(4), 66–77. <https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol11no4.5>
- Apat, H. C. M., Sarias, K. J. M., Tomarong, M. T., & Bacatan, J. R. (2023). The Influence of Oral Communication on the Learning Engagement of Students. *Canadian Journal of Language and Literature Studies*, 3(4), 44–58. <https://doi.org/10.53103/cjlls.v3i4.104>
- Barroga, E. & Mantanguihan, G. (2020). A practical guide to writing quantitative and qualitative research questions and hypotheses in scholarly articles. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2022.37.e121>.
- Bhandari, P. (2021, February 15). What is quantitative research? | Definition uses and methods. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>

- Chentez, J. R., Felicilda, J. V., Felisilda, A. R., & Tabañag, R. E. (2019). Common Problems in Oral Communication Skills Among High School Students. *SMCC Higher Education Research Journal (Teacher Education Journal)*, 1(1), 1–1.
- Cooper, K. M., & Brownell, S. E. (2020). Student anxiety and fear of negative evaluation in active learning science classrooms. In Springer eBooks (pp. 909–925). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33600-4_56
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design, Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods fourth edition (4th Edition ed.)*. (A. Fawaid, & R. Pancasari, Eds.) SAGE Publication Inc.
- Cohen, D. J., & Crabtree, B. F. (2008). Evaluative criteria for qualitative research in health care: controversies and recommendations. *The Annals of Family Medicine*, 6(4), 331-339.
- De Jong, N. H. (2023). A mixed-methods study on the effects of manipulated speaking anxiety on L2 utterance and L2 cognitive fluency. OSF. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/QDR9T>
- Demir, O., Cinar, M., & Keskin, S. (2023). Participation style and social anxiety as predictors of active participation in asynchronous discussion forums and academic achievement. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(9), 11313–11334. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11517-3>
- Dornyei, Z., & Csizer, K. (2002). Motivational Dynamics in Second Language Acquisition Results of a Longitudinal Nationwide Survey. *Applied Linguistics*, 23, 421-462. - References - Scientific Research Publishing. (n.d.).
- Dung, L. Q. (2020). Speaking Anxiety and Language Proficiency among EFL at A University in Vietnam. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 03(09). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v3-i9-01>
- Fiveable P., Okoro, E. A., Priest, R., & Patton, G. (2022). Communication Apprehension in the workplace: Focusing on inclusion. *Business and Professional Communication Quarterly*, 86(1), 52–75. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23294906221129599>
- Han, S., Li, Y., & Haider, S. A. (2022). Impact of Foreign language classroom anxiety on Higher education students' Academic success: Mediating role of emotional intelligence and moderating influence of classroom environment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.945062>
- Long, M. H. (1996). The role of the linguistic environment in second language acquisition. In W. C. Ritchie, & T. K. Bhatia (Eds.), *Handbook of second language acquisition* (pp. 413-468). New York Academic Press. - References - Scientific Research Publishing. (n.d.).
- Male, H. (2018). Foreign Language Learners' Anxiety in Language Skills Learning: A Case study at Universitas Kristen Indonesia. *JET (Journal of English Teaching)*, 4(3), 170. <https://doi.org/10.33541/jet.v4i3.854>
- Montijo, S. (2022). Public speaking anxiety: What is it and tips to overcome it. Psych Central. <https://psychcentral.com/anxiety/public-speaking-anxiety>
- Norton, B. (2000). *Identity and Language Learning Gender, Ethnicity and Educational Change*. Harlow Pearson Education. - References - Scientific Research Publishing.
- Pascual, L. P. (2019). Exposure to English linguistic environment and oral proficiency of first year college students in Davao del Norte. *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on E-Education, E-Business, E-Management and E-Learning - IC4E '19*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3306500.3306525>
- Rood, M. M. S. J., & De Jong, N. H. (2023). A mixed-methods study on the effects of manipulated speaking anxiety on L2 utterance and L2 cognitive fluency. *Journal of the European Second Language Association*, 7(1), 60–74. <https://doi.org/10.22599/jesla.96>
- Saeed, M. A. (2024). Anxiety in learning English as a foreign language: Causes, effects, and coping strategies. *International Journal of Humanities and Education Research*, 6(2), 89–93. <https://doi.org/10.33545/26649799.2024.v6.i2b.95>

- Winaryo, S., & Gusdian, R. I. (2021). Measuring English Language Education Department students' speaking fluency level. *Wanastra Jurnal Bahasa Dan Sastra*, 13(1), 13–18. <https://doi.org/10.31294/w.v13i1.9812>
- Young, D. J. (2022). The relationship between anxiety and foreign language oral proficiency ratings. *Utk*. https://www.academia.edu/8100510/The_Relationship_Between_Anxiety_and_Foreign_Language_Oral_Proficiency_Ratings
- Zhang, J. (2021). Analysis on English Learning Anxiety of Non-English Major College Students during the COVID-19 Epidemic. *Journal of Xihua University (Philosophy & Social Sciences)*, 3, 103-114. - References - Scientific Research Publishing.